

Morphological Characteristics of the Kidneys in Laboratory Animals after Acute Irradiation with Preventive Biocorrection

Sukhrob O. NURULLOYEV

Bukhara State Medical Institute Named After Abu Ali ibn Sina,
Bukhara, Uzbekistan

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ABSTRACT

This study investigates histomorphological changes in the kidneys of laboratory albino rats exposed to acute radiation and evaluates the protective effects of preventive biocorrection. Histological examination showed that in 30% of cases the renal histoarchitectonics remained unchanged, while in 36.7% the renal capsule exhibited uniform thickness and in 70% the glomeruli preserved their normal morphology. In animals that received preventive biocorrection, the frequency of pathological alterations—such as hydropic degeneration of the tubular epithelium, glomerular deformation, and vascular congestion—was significantly reduced compared with irradiated rats that did not undergo biocorrection.

Furthermore, reparative regeneration processes in glomerular podocytes and tubular epithelial cells were observed only in the biocorrected group (23.3%). These findings demonstrate that preventive biocorrection helps maintain renal structural integrity, reduces radiation-induced damage, and activates reparative regenerative mechanisms. Thus, the proposed preventive biocorrection method is biologically safe, clinically effective, and economically feasible, offering promising potential for mitigating radiation-induced renal injury.

KEYWORDS

Acute radiation; kidney; histoarchitectonics; preventive biocorrection; hydropic dystrophy; reparative regeneration; glomeruli; podocytes; morphological changes; nephron integrity.

Humans are exposed to various types and levels of radiation throughout their lives. In addition to natural background radiation, individuals may receive ionizing radiation (IR) from radiotherapy equipment as part of medical treatment [1]. For example, in treatments for leukemia, an absorbed dose of 12–15 Gy may be delivered to the patient's body, typically administered in 8–12 fractions, two to three times per day, over 4–5 days a week for several weeks [2,3]. Humans of any age may also be subjected to excessive ionizing radiation due to nuclear accidents [4].

Since Soviet cosmonaut Yuri Gagarin first orbited Earth in the Vostok spacecraft on 12 April 1961, human activity in outer space has expanded significantly [5].

As of 26 September 2019, a total of 565 people have traveled to space, and 12 have walked on the Moon. Collectively, they have spent more than 29,000 person-days in space, including over 100 person-days of spacewalks [6].

As the number of space travelers and the duration of missions increased in the last century, understanding the effects of the space environment on the human body has become a critical priority for organizations involved in space exploration. Continuous exposure to IR causes biological damage, leading to serious health consequences [7,8]. Thus, mitigating its negative effects on quality of life, human health, and longevity is an important research priority.

The nematode *Caenorhabditis elegans*, a widely used model organism, has been extensively studied to assess the effects of radiation at the molecular, cellular, and organismal levels, providing insights relevant to human health [9].

C. elegans are free-living, non-hazardous, non-infectious worms that inhabit decaying vegetation and feed on microbes (Figure 1) [10]. They are easy to maintain in laboratory conditions due to their small adult size (approximately 1 mm in length) and short life cycle [11].

Anatomically and genomically, *C. elegans* share several similarities with humans, including the presence of muscle tissue, an integrated nervous system, a digestive tract, reproductive organs, and fat-storage structures [12]. The nematode has approximately 20,000 predicted protein-coding genes, more than one-third of which are homologous to human genes [13], and exhibits DNA damage responses similar to those observed in humans [14]. Owing to these characteristics, *C. elegans* is one of the most suitable model organisms for studying the effects of ionizing and non-ionizing radiation.

This model has been used in research on apoptosis, muscle atrophy, radiation-induced damage, metabolic disorders, and aging, benefiting from its rapid life cycle compared to mammals [15]. It is also widely employed to investigate embryogenesis, morphogenesis, neural function, and behavior [16].

The indirect effects of radiation are primarily associated with the radiolysis of water, which constitutes 75–80% of total body mass. Studies have shown that ionization of water generates radicals with oxidizing and alkaline properties [6, pp. 738–740]. During irradiation, the formation of atomic hydrogen, hydroperoxyl radicals, and hydrogen peroxide is particularly significant. These reactive oxygen species participate in enzymatic reactions that transform active sulfhydryl groups into inactive disulfide compounds. As a result, the catalytic activity of thiol enzyme systems decreases, leading to a marked reduction in nuclear DNA and RNA levels and impairing their renewal processes [13].

Materials and Methods

To investigate morphological changes in the kidneys of laboratory animals under conditions of acute and chronic irradiation, **90 male white outbred rats** weighing **160–180 g** were selected. All animals were obtained from the same vivarium and were of the same age (3 months). They were housed under standard vivarium conditions: relative humidity **50–60%**, temperature **19–22 °C**, and a **12 h light/dark cycle**.

The rats were divided into **three main groups**:

First main group (acute irradiation): 30 rats received a single total-body dose of **5 Gy** and were maintained on the standard vivarium diet.

Second main group (chronic irradiation): 30 rats received **0.2 Gy** of irradiation daily for **20 days** (total dose **4 Gy**) and were kept on the standard diet.

Control group: 30 intact rats received neither irradiation nor the *Lactopropolis-AWL* supplement and were maintained on the standard diet.

The first and second main groups were further subdivided: **1a subgroup:** acute irradiation + *Lactopropolis-AWL* supplement (n = 15); **1b subgroup:** acute irradiation without supplement (n = 15); **2a subgroup:** chronic irradiation + *Lactopropolis-AWL* supplement (n = 15); **2b subgroup:** chronic irradiation without supplement (n = 15).

The experimental and control groups were uniform and differed only by a single variable—irradiation (type and dose) and/or administration of the biopreparation—ensuring the validity and reliability of the results obtained.

Results and Discussion

Histological examination of the kidneys of laboratory animals exposed to acute irradiation and receiving preventive biocorrection revealed a range of morphological alterations.

In **30.0% of cases** (n = 9), the **histoarchitectonics of renal tissue remained unchanged** (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Histological view of the kidney from an irradiated albino rat subjected to preventive biocorrection (renal tissue histoarchitectonics preserved; cortical and medullary structures appear largely homogeneous; hematoxylin and eosin stain, 4×10). Such a condition was not observed in the kidneys of irradiated animals that did not receive biocorrection; no irradiated albino rats without morphological changes were identified. This intact histological pattern was observed only in the non-irradiated control animals. In these preparations, most cortical and medullary structures of the kidney maintained a homogeneous appearance.

To continue the assessment, a histological preparation from another experimental animal was examined. In this case, the renal capsule remained unchanged in **36.7%** of observations (n = 11), exhibiting a uniform thickness. The glomeruli preserved their normal morphology in **70.0%** of cases (n = 21), with no signs of deformation. In the tubular epithelium, mild **hydropic dystrophy** was detected in **26.7%** of cases (n = 8). Additionally, narrowing of the tubular lumens was observed in **40.0%** of cases (n = 12) (Figure 2).

Figure 2. Histological view of the kidney from an irradiated albino rat subjected to preventive biocorrection (renal capsule intact with uniform thickness; glomerular morphology preserved; mild hydropic dystrophy of the tubular epithelium (1); narrowing of tubular lumens (2); hematoxylin and eosin stain, 10×10).

A similar pattern was observed in another histological specimen. One of the pathological morphological signs—**mild hydropic dystrophy of the proximal tubular epithelium**—was identified in **26.7%** of cases (n = 8). Hydropic dystrophy, characterized by swelling of renal epithelial cells, was therefore present, albeit infrequently. Additionally, **uneven congestion of pericortical capillaries** was detected in **33.3%** of cases (n = 10). Considering that these capillaries are located in proximity to the nephrons—the primary functional units of the kidney—the potential adverse impact on the initial phase of urine formation becomes evident.

It should also be noted that **narrowing of the tubular lumens** was observed in **40.0%** of cases (n = 12) (Figure 3).

Figure 3. Histological view of the kidney from an irradiated albino rat subjected to preventive biocorrection (mild hydropic dystrophy in the proximal tubular epithelium (1); uneven congestion of pericortical capillaries (2); narrowing of tubular lumens; hematoxylin and eosin stain, 40×10).

To assess the impact of acute radiation exposure and prior preventive biocorrection on the incidence of pathological morphological alterations in the kidney, another histological specimen was examined. The results are presented in Figure 4. As shown, deformation of renal glomeruli associated with hydropic dystrophy of the proximal tubules was identified in 26.7% of cases (n = 8), with glomerular deformation specifically recorded in 30.0% of cases (n = 9). In addition, congestion of the peritubular capillaries of the arterial rete mirabile was observed in 43.3% of cases (n = 13).

Since such vascular and structural alterations impair the formation of primary urine and disrupt the normal activity of nephrons—the structural and functional units of the kidney—it can be concluded that acute irradiation leads to both structural and functional kidney damage.

Figure 4. Histological view of the kidney from an irradiated albino rat subjected to preventive biocorrection (glomerular deformation associated with hydropic dystrophy in proximal tubules (1); congestion of the peritubular capillaries of the arterial *rete mirabile* (2); hematoxylin and eosin stain, 40×10).

In another histological specimen, **reparative regeneration of podocytes** in the glomerular capillaries was observed in **23.3%** of cases (n = 7) (Figure 5). Podocytes, the epithelial cells of Bowman’s capsule forming its third filtration layer, play a critical role in blood filtration. Given their essential function, the presence of reparative regeneration indicates a beneficial effect on renal filtration capacity.

Additionally, the cavity of the **Shumlyansky–Bowman capsule** exhibited a uniform width in **90.0%** of cases (n = 27). Similar to the glomerular structures, an **enhanced reparative regeneration process** was also detected in the proximal tubular epithelium in **23.3%** of animals (n = 7). Since reparative regeneration represents the replacement of cells or tissues damaged by pathological processes, these findings clearly indicate the restoration of renal structures.

Importantly, no such regenerative phenomena were observed in the kidneys of irradiated laboratory animals **without** preventive biocorrection.

Therefore, we have substantial grounds to consider preventive biocorrection as an indirect but significant factor contributing to the activation of reparative regeneration in renal tissue.

Figure 5. Histological view of the kidney from an irradiated albino rat subjected to preventive biocorrection (reparative regeneration of podocytes in the glomerular capillaries (1); Shumlyansky–Bowman capsule cavity of uniform width (2); enhanced reparative regeneration in the proximal tubular epithelium (3); hematoxylin and eosin stain, 80×10).

The obtained results were compared with those of irradiated albino rats that did not receive preventive biocorrection, and the findings are summarized in *Table 1*.

Table 1. Incidence of morphological changes in the kidneys of irradiated albino rats with and without preventive biocorrection.

Morphological changes	Acute radiation-exposed			
	PB was carried out		No PB was carried out	
	Abso lute	%	Ab solute	%
The histoarchitecture and capsule of the kidney are unchanged.	4	13,3	11	36,7
Hydropic dystrophy of the tubular epithelium	26	86,7	8	26,7
The shape of the balls is deformed.	26	86,7	9	30,0
Focal necrosis in the tubular epithelium	24	80,0	0	0
The integrity of the capillaries of the balls	23	76,7	0	0
Narrowed renal tubule spaces	21	70,0	12	40,0
Pericortical vascular engorgement	21	70,0	10	33,3
Homogeneous protein structures in the proximal tubule spaces	16	53,3	0	0
Bowman's space is narrowed	14	46,7	3	10,0
Reparative regeneration of glomerular capillaries podocytes	0	0	7	23,3
Reparative regeneration in tubular epithelia	0	0	7	23,3

Note: PB – preventive biocorrection.

As shown, positive outcomes were achieved for all evaluated indicators. The proportion of animals with preserved renal histoarchitectonics and an intact renal capsule was significantly higher among those that underwent preventive biocorrection (**36.7%**) compared with those that did not (**13.3%**).

In contrast, pathological morphological signs—such as **hydropic dystrophy of the tubular epithelium** (26.7% vs. 86.7%) and **deformation of glomerular structures** (30.0% vs. 86.7%)—were substantially more frequent in irradiated rats that did not receive biocorrection. These findings clearly demonstrate the protective and reparative effects of preventive biocorrection against radiation-induced renal damage.

In addition, **focal necrosis in the tubular epithelium**, **congestion of glomerular capillaries**, and **homogeneous protein structures within the proximal tubular lumens** were frequently observed in animals that did not receive preventive biocorrection (80.0%, 76.7%, and 53.3%, respectively), while these pathological signs were **completely absent (0%)** in rats treated with biocorrection. Conversely, morphological features such as **reparative regeneration of podocytes in glomerular capillaries** and **reparative regeneration in the tubular epithelium**—not detected at all (0%) in irradiated albino rats without biocorrection—were recorded in **23.3%** of animals that underwent preventive biocorrection. Overall, all comparative indicators demonstrate clear and consistent advantages in favor of preventive biocorrection, highlighting its protective and reparative influence on renal tissue subjected to acute radiation exposure.

Conclusion

The results of this study clearly demonstrate the protective and restorative potential of preventive biocorrection in mitigating radiation-induced kidney damage in albino rats. Animals subjected to acute irradiation typically exhibited pronounced pathological alterations, including hydropic dystrophy, glomerular deformation, narrowing of tubular lumens, vascular congestion, and focal necrosis. However, the application of preventive biocorrection led to a significant reduction in the incidence and severity of these detrimental structural changes. Furthermore, features of reparative regeneration—such as the recovery of podocytes within glomerular capillaries and the regeneration of tubular epithelial cells—were observed exclusively in the biocorrected animals, indicating activation of intrinsic repair mechanisms that were entirely absent in the untreated irradiated group.

These findings underscore the multifaceted benefits of preventive biocorrection, which not only preserves nephron integrity but also supports functional restoration following radiation exposure. The marked improvement in renal histoarchitectonics, stabilization of vascular structures, and normalization of Bowman's capsule morphology collectively point to a systemic protective influence exerted by the biocorrective preparation. Importantly, the absence of adverse morphological outcomes in biocorrected animals confirms the biological safety and compatibility of the applied method.

Based on the accumulated experimental evidence, the developed preventive biocorrection strategy can be regarded as biologically safe, medically reliable, economically feasible, and socially relevant.

Its demonstrated efficacy in reducing radiation-induced damage and promoting reparative regeneration suggests promising potential for broader application in radiobiology, occupational health, radiation medicine, and emergency preparedness. Future studies may explore its molecular mechanisms, long-term effects, and translational applicability in clinical and environmental settings.

Overall, the present research highlights preventive biocorrection as a valuable and innovative approach for protecting renal tissues from the harmful consequences of ionizing radiation.

References

1. Abrashova T.V., Gushchin Ya.A., Kovaleva M.A., Rybakova A.V., Selezneva A.I., Sokolova A.P., Khodko S.V. *Spravochnik: Fiziologicheskie, biokhimicheskie i biometricheskie pokazateli normy eksperimentalnykh zhivotnykh*. St. Petersburg: Lema Publishing; 2013. 116 p.
2. Artashyan O.S., Yushkov B.G., Khramsova Yu.S. Morphological aspects of mast cell involvement in the formation of the general adaptation syndrome. *Tavrisheskiy Mediko-Biologicheskiy Vestnik*. 2012;15(3-1):22–25.
3. Arkhipova L.V., Glazkova P.A., Glazkov A.A., Bychenkov O.A., Kulikov D.A. A method to reduce mortality from radiation exposure in experimental animals. Registration date: 17.01.2019.
4. Barsukov N.P. *Sitologiya, gistologiya, embriologiya: Uchebnoe posobie*. St. Petersburg: Lan; 2020. 248 p.
5. Belyaeva Ye.A., Kriventsov M.A. Experimental modeling of xenogenic cerebrospinal fluid application as a protective agent during radiation damage of the submandibular salivary gland. *Ukrainskiy Morfologichniy Almanakh*. 2014;12(2):106–108.
6. Vasin M.V., Ushakov I.B., Kovtun V.Yu., Semenova L.A., Koroleva L.V., Galkin A.A., Afanasev R.V. Therapeutic effect of long-term melatonin administration on the course and mortality of experimental acute radiation sickness. *Byulleten Eksperimentalnoy Biologii i Meditsiny*. 2013;156(12):738–740.
7. Vorontsova Z.A., Zyuzina V.V. Immune effects of low-dose γ -irradiation in an experiment. In: *Fundamentalnye i prikladnye issledovaniya v meditsine*. Paris; 2011. *Mezhdunarodnyy Zhurnal Prikladnykh i Fundamentalnykh Issledovaniy*. 2011;11:80–81.
8. Vladimirov S.N., Skorik A.S. Modern problems of radiobiology. *Mezhdunarodnyy Zhurnal Eksperimentalnogo Obrazovaniya*. 2014;8-3:63–64.
9. Galstyan I.A., Suvorova L.A., Nadezhina N.M., Kozlova M.G., Nugis V.Yu. Blood status in the late period of acute radiation sickness. *Saratovskiy Nauchno-Meditsinskiy Zhurnal*. 2013;9(4):882–890.
10. Gaynutdinov T.R., Vagin K.N., Nizamov R.N. A method for obtaining a preparation for treating combined radiation–thermal injuries. *Uchenye Zapiski UO VGAVM*. 2018;54(4):32–36.
11. Gudkov I.N., Kudyasheva A.G., Moskalyov A.A. *Radiobiologiya s osnovami radioekologii*. Syktyvkar: Syktyvkar State University Press; 2015. 512 p.
12. Grebenyuk A.N., Zargarova N.I., Kondakov A.Yu., Legeza V.I. Modeling of combined radiation injury caused by whole-body gamma irradiation and X-ray skin burn in rats. *Meditsinskaya Radiologiya i Radiatsionnaya Bezopasnost*. 2016;61(2):20–24.
13. Demyashkin G.A., Koryakin S.N., Stepanova Yu.Yu., Shchekin V.I., Shegay P.V. Morphological characteristics of rat kidneys after targeted electron irradiation at doses of 2, 4, and 6 Gy. *Zhurnal dlya Professionalov ot Professionalov*. 2017;6:1–7.
14. *Directive 2010/63/EU of the European Parliament and of the Council on the protection of animals used for scientific purposes*. St. Petersburg: Rus-LASA; 2012. 48 p.
15. Dorozhkina O.V., Bulyanina T.M., Ivanov A.A. The influence of individual and group housing of mice on the level of radioresistance. *Saratovskiy Nauchno-Meditsinskiy Zhurnal*. 2015;11(4):653–656.
16. Yeregin P.S., Pigaleva N.A., Murzabekov M.B., Lebedev V.G., Lazareva N.L., Yeregin I.I., Pulin A.A., Osipov A.N., Bushmanov A.Yu., Kotenko K.V. Study of the effectiveness of autologous cell products derived from adipose tissue for the treatment of severe local radiation injuries. *Saratovskiy Nauchno-Meditsinskiy Zhurnal*. 2014;10(4):838–844.